

CHARACTERIZATION OF SMC FLOW BY THIN DISC COMPRESSION TESTS

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ABSTRACT

Thin discs of a Sheet Moulding Compound (SMC/R) were produced by compression moulding for assessing the flow behaviour of the material.

For a given SMC/R, a model was developed enabling the prediction of the moulding force as a function of the initial pre-form. This model is an equation of the type $F = F_0 \psi^d$

The experimental results were intended to predict the influence of the processing parameters on the equipment requirements and to verify the good aptitude of the material for moulding.

Keywords: SMC flow, Compression moulding, Sheet Moulding Compound.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years an important increment of the consumption of SMC was observed in the production of components by compression moulding, especially for automotive, electric and electronic applications.

The quality of SMC parts is dependent on process variables such as mould temperature, pre-form dimensions and platen displacement rate, and the degree of polymerization of the SMC compound prior to moulding. These influence the flow during compression and the final properties of the parts. Therefore a tight control of these variables is fundamental in the production of quality products.

The objective of this work was the establishment of a model relating the pre-form dimensions to the force requirements of the equipment, and the analysis of the influence of that variable on the moulding behaviour of a given SMC/R.

2. THEORY

The flow behaviour of polymeric materials during moulding has been modelled using the simultaneous solution of three constitutive equations (continuity, motion and energy) and a rheological equation [e.g. 1,2].

For the case of a disc squeezed between two plates (Figure 1), the solution involving a power law equation was presented by Leider and Bird [3,4].

We have applied the same approach [5,6,7] to the case of SMC materials. The following simplifying assumptions were considered: i) incompressibility of the material; ii) quasi-stationary process; iii)

gravity negligible; iv) no-slip at the mould surface; v) laminar flow; vi) negligible energy dissipation, and viii) isothermic process implying that the polymerization was also negligible during flow.

Figure 1. Geometry and cylindrical coordinate system for the SMC disc compression.

The Leider and Bird equation [3] is of the form

$$F = \pi \left[\frac{2n+1}{2n} \right]^n \frac{K}{(n+3)} \frac{(-\dot{h})^n}{(h(t))^{(2n+1)}} [R(t)]^{(n+3)} \quad (1)$$

where: F is the compression force

n and K are material constants in the power law equation $\tau = -K \dot{\gamma}^n$
 $h(t)$ and $R(t)$ are moulding dimensions at the instant t (according to Fig.1)
 \dot{h} is the platen displacement rate

In order to apply Eq. (1) to the case of the SMC mouldings in this work a dimensionless moulding thickness was defined as:

$$\frac{1}{\psi} = \frac{h(t)}{h_0} = \frac{2h_0 - \Delta l}{2h_0} \quad (2)$$

where: Δl is the displacement of the press platen
 $2h_0$ is the initial pre-form thickness.

If on Eq. (1), $(-\dot{h})$ is replaced by $\frac{V_p}{2}$ and $R(t)$ by $R_0 R(\psi)$, the force on the disc is given by:

$$F = \pi \left[\frac{2n+1}{2n} \right]^n \frac{K}{(n+3)} \frac{(V_p)^n R_0^{(n+3)}}{2^n h_0^{(2n+1)}} \psi^{2.5(n+1)} \quad (3)$$

If the following constants are defined

$$F_0 = \pi \left[\frac{2n+1}{2n} \right]^n \frac{K}{(n+3)} \frac{(V_p)^n R_0^{(n+3)}}{2^n h_0^{(2n+1)}} \quad (4)$$

and

$$d = 2.5(n+1) \quad (5)$$

the Eq. (3) takes the more simplified form

$$F = F_o (\psi)^d \quad (6)$$

This equation suggests that in a logarithmic plot of the (F vs. ψ) curve, a straight line should be obtained with an origin intercept, F_o , and a slope, d.

From Eq. (4) and (5) and for a given platen velocity (V_p), it is also possible to relate the initial forces necessary to squeeze two discs of different volumes having an equal initial thickness ($2h_o$) by:

$$\frac{F_o^*}{F_o} = \left[\frac{R_o}{R_o^*} \right]^{\frac{d}{2.5} + 2} \quad (7)$$

where F_o , R_o and F_o^* , R_o^* , are the initial forces and radii of discs of volumes V and V_o^* , respectively.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

3.1. Material

A fire retardant SMC/R with 30% of random 25mm type E-glass fibres was used. The material is manufactured by Fiberpachs,S.A.(Spain) and used in electrical boxes. For this work circular pre-forms were prepared with different diameters.

3.2. Equipment

An instrumented mould was designed for the production of 200 mm in diameter discs. The mould platens are independently heated by electric cartridges of 5,7 and 7,92 kW.

The processing was carried with an hydraulic press of 400 kN. A trace of the force and displacement variation was obtained for each test.

3.3. Procedure

The tests were carried according to the schedule indicated in Table 1. The pre-forms weighing 145 g were prepared with diameters and thickness varying so that different levels of initial shear rate or of ratio between the final and the initial shear rate, $\dot{\gamma}_f/\dot{\gamma}_o$, were created. The final moulding thickness was of 2,5 mm.

Table 1

Test ref.	Initial diameter -D _o - (mm)	Initial thickness -2h _o - (mm)	$\frac{\dot{\gamma}_f}{\dot{\gamma}_o}$ (dimensionless)	Mould Temperature -T- (°C)	Press Platen velocity -V _p - (mm/s)
a	60	27,8	411,5	120	1
b	80	15,6	97,7		
c	100	10,0	32,0		
d	120	6,9	12,9		
e	140	5,1	5,9		

From the force-displacement traces, the log-log (force vs. ψ) curves were derived. An example is shown in Figure 2. The analysis of the log-log curve on its linear zone enables the calculation of the constants, F_0 and d , defined in Eq. (5) and (6).

Figure 2. Experimental results for a pre-form of 120 mm.

3.4. Results and discussion

The experimental force vs. displacement curves show four characteristic zones (as in Figure 2.a)):

- Zone I - is characterized by reduced and almost constant value of the force, corresponding to the pre-form consolidation and elimination of the trapped air; rigorously this zone should not be considered as an effective part of the compression process,
- Zone II - the applied force rises rapidly, the material behaves like a solid and the preform heating takes place causing the compressive modulus to reduce progressively,
- Zone III - corresponds to the actual flow behaviour of the SMC; the temperature flow from the mould to the material may be assumed as stopped.
- Zone IV - corresponds to the final stage of the mould filling; the force increases rapidly corresponding to the pressurisation of the material.

For the derivation of the (force vs. ψ) curves only the zones II to IV were considered. It may be observed that these curves show a linear trend in zone III, corresponding to the moulding period when the flow is well established (Figure 2.b)).

Also, the pre-form dimensions affect the characteristic constants, F_0 and d (Figure 3). Increasing the pre-form diameter, or decreasing its thickness, causes the value of F_0 to increase and the slope d to decrease. It may be observed that the decreasing of F_0 with the thickness is slower than the predict by Eq. (4). This suggests that heat transfer plays a fundamental role in the process.

Figure 3. Force versus ψ curves for different pre-form diameters.

The experimental data can be worked out again to relate the characteristic values, F_0 and d , in order to the initial thickness, $2h_0$, as shown in Figures 4 and 5. This shows that increasing the initial thickness causes F_0 to decrease and d to increase almost linearly.

Figure 4. Variation of F_0 with the initial pre-form thickness

Figure 5- Variation of d with the initial pre-form thickness

This information may be of value for a dual purpose: firstly, to predict the maximum force required for compression moulding a part from a given pre-form, and secondly for quality control purposes in order to check quickly the adequacy of a batch of raw material.

For example, if one would like to predict the force required for moulding a disc with diameter of 300 mm and 2 mm of thickness from a pre-form of 150 mm and 8 mm thickness, the procedure would be as follows:

1. Calculate the final ψ : $\psi_f = \frac{h_o}{h_f} = \frac{8}{2} = 4$
2. From Figure 4 read F_o^* : $F_o^* = 27,5 \text{ kN}$
3. In our case R_o^* is: $R_o^* = \sqrt{\frac{100^2 \times 2,5}{8}} = 56 \text{ mm}$
4. From Figure 5 read d : $d = 0,9$
5. From Eq. (7) calculate F_o : $F_o = 27,5 \times \left[\frac{0,15}{0,056} \right]^{\frac{0,9}{2,5} + 2} = 281,3 \text{ kN}$
6. Using equation $F = F_o \psi^d$ calculated the required value of F :

$$F = 281,3 \times 4^{0,9} = 979,5 \text{ kN}$$

For quality control, for example, all that a technician would be required to do was to test a pre-form of given dimensions and comparing the starting point of zone II and the end point of zone III of a curve like that of Figure 2 with the corresponding ones of a reference curve.

4. Conclusions

The compression moulding of thin discs appears to be a viable method to characterize the flow characteristics of SMC.

The influence of the flow behaviour on the compression requirements may be described by the equation:

$$F = F_o \psi^d$$

where F_o and d are parameters determined experimentally.

The use of this equation is convenient for predicting the compression force required for production.

Also, the findings of the work suggest that this test may be used for quality control of compound batches.

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References

1. Tadmor, Z. and Gogos, C.; *Principles of Polymer Processing*, Willey, New York, 1979,

2. Tucker III, C., *Fundamentals of Computer Modeling for Polymer Processing*, Hanser, New York, 1989.
3. Leider, P. and Bird, R., *Squeezing Flow Between Parallel Disks I. Theoretical Analysis*, Ind. Eng. Chem. Fundam., 13, , 1974 p. 336-341.
4. Leider, P., *Squeezing Flow Between Parallel Disks II. Experimental Results*, Ind. Eng. Chem. Fundam., 13, 1974, pp. 342-346.
5. Burns, R., *Polyester Molding Compounds*, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 1982.
6. Lee, L.J., Fan, J.D., Kim, J., Im, Y.-T., *Flow Analysis of Sheet Molding Compounds in Compression Molding*, Intern. Polym Proc., VI, 1, Hanser, Munich, 1991, pp. 61-72
7. Isayev, A.I., *Injection and Compression Molding Fundamentals*, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1987.